

Original article

Hematological and Biochemical Parameters in Donkey (*Equus asinus*) during Colostrum Production

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Abstract

It is very important to analyze the hematological and biochemical profile in the donkey during the colostrum period, because these changes that bring us information about the health of the animals. The data obtained during the colostrum period were compared with those obtained during the lactation period. The biochemical parameters have a high average value on the first postpartum day (the highest values) and they decrease on day 5 postpartum. On day 30, it can be observed that all biochemical parameters of the blood have lower mean values, some similar to those obtained from donkeys from lactations 1-4.

Keywords: *colostral period, hematological, biochemical parameters.*

1. Introduction

There are different data in the literature for haematological and biochemical parameters in donkey. These changes for the parameters are determined by the following factors: exploitation technique, lactation, colostrum, feeding, animal health, age of the animal, effort made by the animal, species, breed [1 - 5]. Feeding practices can have a significant impact on milk production and metabolic profile in donkeys.

High triglyceride levels are reported [4, 5]. Regarding the parturition period, the leukocyte level showed increases after 10 days of parturition [1, 2].

A diet high in sugar and fat influences serum creatinine levels. They may vary depending on protein-rich diets in donkeys with more developed muscle mass.

The aim of the study is to analyze the influence of postpartum day on hematological and biochemical indicators of blood in donkey (*Equus asinus*).

2. Material and Method

A number of 10 blood samples were collected (for the analysis of hematological and biochemical parameters) according to the postpartum day (day 1 and day 5) and day 30 of lactation.

Blood samples after harvest were kept cold until analysis was performed. The apparatus used for biochemical analysis is the semiautomatic analyzer (FAX 1904 Plus, GMI). Hematological parameters analysis was performed with the Abacus Junior automatic device.

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3. Results and Discussions

Table 1 and 2 show the mean values and variability for donkeys during colostrum and day 30 of lactation. ALT (U/L), GGT (U/L), behaves similar to other biochemical parameters in that they present

the highest values in the postpartum period (the first 5 days) and decrease on day 30 of lactation. Urea (mmol/l) shows the highest values on day 1, postpartum (6.23 ± 0.73) (mmol/L) and decreases on day 5 postpartum to 5.58 ± 0.52 mmol/L (Table 1).

Table 1. Mean value and variability for biochemical parameters of donkey blood depending on postpartum day and day 30

Parameter	Day 1 (n=10)		Day 5 (n=10)		Day 30 (n=10)	
	X±sx	V%	X±sx	V%	X±sx	V%
Urea (mmol/L)	6.23±0.73	26.14	5.58±0.52	21.01	5.84±0.38	14.48
Total protein (g/L)	64.10±1.27	4.42	62.58±2.31	8.25	59.50±0.73	2.75
Glucose (mmol/L)	6.18±0.53	19.06	6.07±0.33	12.02	4.63±0.29	14.09
Albumin (g/L)	25.92±1.14	9.80	27.04±0.71	5.86	23.89±1.47	13.78
Creatinine (µmol/L)	146.9±2.94	4.48	126.24±4.79	8.48	104.92±2.56	5.46
Cholesterol (mmol/L)	2.28±0.15	14.5	2.10±0.25	27.15	2.04±0.30	32.63
K (mmol/L)	6.02±0.08	2.99	5.74±0.35	13.54	5.56±0.28	11.44
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	0.73±0.07	20.73	0.87±0.04	9.92	0.74±0.06	17.99
Total calcium (mmol / L)	3.78±0.09	5.06	3.42±0.27	17.47	3.02±0.23	17.02
Na (mmol/L)	143.6±1.91	2.98	137.98±3.59	5.82	135.6±5.14	8.48
Total bilirubin (mmol/l)	10.62±0.48	10.06	10.79±0.63	12.99	9.38±1.02	24.34
Mg (mmol/L)	0.95±0.04	9.18	0.85±0.03	7.85	0.78±0.07	8.64
ALT (U/L)	16.41±0.67	9.18	15.76±0.64	9.09	14.86±1.08	16.25
AST (U/L)	266.68±4.47	3.74	233.14±2.85	2.73	243.6±9.26	8.5
ALP (U/L)	244.12±2.65	2.43	246.42±5.15	4.68	210±6.06	6.45
GGT (U/L)	92.36±1.26	3.05	88.10±1.46	3.71	76.9±3.37	9.80
CK (U/L)	126.24±4.79	8.48	206.6±6.07	6.57	246.8±6.91	6.26

V- variability; X –mean value; n- number of blood samples.

The total protein (g/L) shows the highest average values on day 1 postpartum, (64.10 ± 1.27), decreases in the following days, reaching the average value of (62.58 ± 2.31) on day 5 postpartum and reaches the value of (59.50 ± 0.73) on day 30 of lactation (Table 1).

Mg (mmol/L), total bilirubin (mmol/L), Na (mmol/L) and total calcium (mmol/L) show the highest values in the postpartum period. WBC (G/L) shows the highest level on day 1 postpartum of 14.16 ± 0.86 (G/L) and decreases on day 5 postpartum to 11.90 ± 0.71 (G/L) and reaches the lowest level in day 30, respectively (10.74 ± 0.33).

EOS (%) shows the highest average values on day 1 and 5 postpartum.

Iwona and Eugeniusz (2014) report an increase in EOS with age [7], similar to studies reported by Girardi et al. (2013), and Horáčková et al. (2017) [4, 5]. Folch et al. (1997) report a decrease in EOS with increasing age [3].

LYM varies within the interval 7.72 ± 0.39 (g/L) on day 1 postpartum and 5.93 ± 0.81 (g/L) on day 30 of lactation. HCT (L/L) shows the highest mean values on day 1 postpartum of 0.65 ± 0.07 (L/L) and the lowest values were noted on day 30, 0.19 ± 0.02 (L/L).

These values fall within the reference values for this species. Hematological parameters are significantly influenced by postpartum day. The

highest average values are on day 1 postpartum, decrease on day 5 postpartum and reach lower values, similar to those of normal lactation (Table 2).

Table 2. Mean value and variability for hematological parameters of donkey blood according to postpartum day and day 30

Parameter	Day 1 (n=10)		Day 5 (n=10)		Day 30 (n=10)	
	X±sx	V%	X±sx	V%	X±sx	V%
WBC (G/L)	14.16±0.86	13.54	11.90±0.71	13.29	10.74±0.33	6.87
RBC (T/L)	7.92±0.19	5.24	6.84±0.18	5.94	6.75±0.45	14.79
Hb (g/L)	144.20±3.06	4.74	138±5.14	8.33	133±6.67	11.22
HCT (l/L)	0.65±0.07	23.21	0.58±0.07	27.12	0.19±0.02	23.31
MCV (fl)q	69.68±1.74	5.59	65.98±3.36	11.37	58.94±3.23	11.26
NEU (%)	57.96±0.91	3.52	48.34±1.24	5.72	44.38±2.84	14.29
LYM (%)	60.8±1.07	3.93	56.8±1.53	6.02	54.8±2.06	8.40
MON (%)	1.79±0.09	11.01	1.64±0.09	12.23	1.37±0.08	15.30
MON (g/L)	0.23±0.03	28.99	0.18±0.02	25.0	0.17±0.13	16.9
NEU (g/L)	3.96±0.10	5.40	2.92±0.17	12.86	3.01±0.11	8.03
LYM (g/L)	7.72±0.39	11.42	5.88±0.32	12.35	5.93 ±0.81	10.49
EOS (%)	4.60±0.39	19.01	4.80±0.33	15.21	3.89±0.31	17.83
PLT (G/L)	3.93±0.08	4.69	3.40±0.19	12.46	3.43±0.31	19.99
MCHC (g/L)	381±4.87	2.86	358.6±5.09	3.17	321.8±4.0	2.78
BAS (%)	0.074±0.02	8.48	0.03±0.01	17.1	0.18±0.02	16.17

V- variability; X – mean value; n- number of blood samples.

Biochemical tests evaluate and indicate the health of the body, the functions of the organs (including the kidneys and liver) according to the metabolic changes in the body [6]. The results of the study published by Iwona and Eugeniusz (2014) indicate a beneficial effect of pasture management and outdoor access on the health of dairy animals [7].

4. Conclusions

The hematological and biochemical parameters of blood in donkeys during the postpartum period and on day 30 of lactation are significantly modified compared to normal lactation. The values for hematological and biochemical parameters reach the highest values on days 1 and 5 post partum, after which they decrease on day 30.

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